

A Comparative Study of Information System's Security by Using Graphs

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ABSTRACT

This paper illustrates that all the projects to design or develop secure information system for processing classified information have had a formal mathematical model like graphs for security as part of the top level definition of the system. The different graph models provide as a precise description of the behavior desired of the security relevant portions of the system. In this paper, an attempt is made to explore the different graphs that can be used in the construction of information system's security and each graph has its individual implications.

INTRODUCTION

Recent research papers in the area of Information System's Security witness how the business and others events are performed for security purposes of the hidden valuable information to improve the vital business operations like process, flow, data organization and social structures Brien [1]. Pursuing on this line, many system's security tools are developed in the market and the commercial interest of these security tools towards the business domain is mounting due to the increasing awareness of the companies to incorporate effectively the same in the cross functional entities Grigori, Casati, Dayal and Shan [2]. To take the right decision, the information's security is essential Wilson and Sharda [3] & Cavusoglu, Mishra and Raghunathan [4].

As global networks expand, the interconnection of the world's information systems, the smooth operation of communication and computing solutions become vital. However, recurring events such as virus and worm attacks and the success of criminal attackers illustrate the weaknesses in current information technologies and the need to provide heightened security for these systems.

The main aim of this paper is to suggest a suitable information system's security that extracts all inherent valuable information based on the above perspectives for effective decisions. The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section-2 explores the relevant information related to matrices and are presented as graphs in Section-3. In Section-4, a suggestive framework of the same is also presented whereas Section-5 concludes the paper.

MATRICES MODELS

There are different types of matrices like design structure matrix, incidence matrix, M_n -matrix etc., which are closely connected to the construction of security designs, codes and graphs.

Design Structure Matrix

The design structure matrix is a system modeling tool. It has two main strengths:

- (i) It can represent a large number of system elements and their relationships in a compact way that highlights important patterns in the data (such as feedback loops and modules).
- (ii) It is amenable to matrix based analysis techniques, which can be used to improve the structure of the system.

A DSM is a square matrix. The cells along the diagonal represent the system elements, which are often labeled in the rows to the left of the matrix and/or in the columns above the matrix. The off-diagonal cells are used to indicate relationships between the elements. Reading across a row reveals what other elements the element in that row provides outputs to, and scanning a column reveals what other elements the element in that column receives input from. Alternatively, the rows and columns may be switched (without a change of meaning).

It provides a compact and clear representation of a complex system and a capture method for the interactions/interdependencies/interfaces between system elements. It provides a project representation that allows for feedback and cyclic task dependencies. This is extremely important since most engineering applications exhibit such a cyclic property. The DSM representation results in an improved and more realistic execution schedule for the corresponding design activities.

Incidence Matrix

The incidence matrix based on the concepts, 0 and 1 element. It is also called a binary matrix or a (0, 1) matrix. It is helpful to construct its geometric graph without ambiguity. The incidence matrix and the geometric graph contain the same information i.e. just as in any two alternative methods of representation, some properties are more evident in one representation than in the other.

Every column of incidence matrix has exactly two 1's since every edge is incident on exactly two vertices.

- (i) The number of 1's in each row equals the degree of the corresponding vertex.
- (ii) Identical columns represent parallel edges in the graph.

M_n - Matrix

The M_n - matrix is a symmetric matrix in which all the elements are reduced to mod n and for all multiples of n ; we take n instead of 0. There exists some symmetry in the occurrence of the elements in the two diagonals. It is a singular matrix and hence $\det M_n = 0$. All the elements in the first column and the first row are 1's; except these, in no other column or in no other row there is repetition of the elements when n is prime. When n is not a prime let x_j 's being the columns where $j = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, n-1$, where $x_j = (j+1)$ th column. Then in any column x_j , the element $(1+a) \bmod n$, $a = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, n-1$, repeats for t time and n/t elements repeat in that column, where t is the number of the column. When n is not a prime, depending on the factors of n , the elements in the columns (rows) will be repeated. The repetition occurs as a natural phenomenon of congruence mod n . Let the column $(x_j) = (j+1)$, where $j = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, n-1$, then $x_j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$. Among $0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, n-1$, there may be some factors of n , and $0, 1, n-1$, will never be the factors of n and among the remaining numbers some x_j 's are factors of n and some other x_j 's are factors of a_j 's where $0 < a_j < n-1$. When some x_j is a factor of a_j s.t. $(a_j, n) = x_j$. Thus we have some x_j 's and a_j 's same, and the remaining are co-primes.

When n is a prime only the first elements of 1's will coincide. When n is not a prime the a^{th} elements of (x_j) , (x_j) columns coincide iff $(a-1) \cdot (x_j \sim x_j)$ is a multiple of n .

The main purpose of this matrix is to make use which is the fundamental result that relates the construction of Mutually Orthogonal Latin Squares (MOLS) and Pairwise Balanced Designs (PBD) as given in Wallis[20,22], for defining some matrices to relate to the constructions of BIB and PBIB designs.

CONSTRUCTION OF GRAPHS THROUGH MATRICES

In this section by using these matrices, the graphs will construct. It is given in Bose [5] that a strongly regular graph determines a two associate class PBIB design and a strongly regular graph of order m determines an m -associate class PBIB design. Furthermore, it is shown that the one factorizations of $K_{n,n}$ are equivalent to Latin squares of side n . Recently, Gropp [6] has established a relation between tactical configurations, regular bipartite graphs and certain combinatorial design and discussed about the construction of graphs.

GRAPHS CONSTRUCTED BY DESIGN STRUCTURE MATRIX

Formal concept analysis is a technique for generating clusters of objects and properties, given a bipartite graph representing the relations between the objects and properties. The method for generating overlapping clusters (a cover rather than a partition) is discussed by Jardine and Sibson.

A natural object cluster is the set of all objects that share a common subset of properties and a natural property cluster is the set of all properties shared by one of the natural object clusters.

Natural property clusters correspond one-for-one with natural object clusters, and a concept is a pair containing both a natural property cluster and its corresponding natural object cluster. The family of these concepts obeys the mathematical axioms defining a bipartite graph of $K_{n,n}$.

Graphs Constructed by Incidence Matrix

Let G be a graph with n vertices, e edges, and no self-loops. Define and n by e matrix let $A = [a_{ij}]$, where n rows correspond to the n vertices and the e columns correspond to the e edges, as follows:

$$a_{ij} = 1 \text{ if } j^{\text{th}} \text{ edge } e_j \text{ is incident on } i^{\text{th}} \text{ vertex } v_i \\ \text{and} \quad = 0 \text{ otherwise.}$$

Case (a)

1	0	0	1	0	1
1	1	0	0	1	0
0	1	1	0	0	1
0	0	1	1	1	0

Incidence Matrix

Graph of the incidence matrix is as follows:

Figure 1

This figure generates complete graph. For the sake of convenience put $n = v$ in the above matrix. Let N be the $v \times b$ incidence matrix of a BIB design with parameters v (being prime).

Case (b)

0	1	0	0
0	0	1	0
1	1	1	1
1	0	0	0
0	0	0	1

Incidence Matrix

Graph of the incidence matrix is as follows:

Figure 2

This figure generates wheel graph, in which intersect vertex shows the center of the graph.

Graphs Constructed by M_n - Matrix

In M_n - matrix, when n is prime and $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, n-1$ and $j = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, n-1$, then there exists just a complete non-planar bipartite graph only. It is shown that there exist PBIB designs, which are associated with these matrices.

For $(i, j) \pmod n$ for $n = 5$ where we take $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$ and $j = 1, 2, 3, 4$, we can get the matrix and the graph as follows:

	1	2	3	4
1				
2				
3				
4				

Figure 3

It is a complete non-planar bipartite graph associated with the above matrix.

APPLICATIONS FOR THESE GRAPHS IN INFORMATION SYSTEM'S SECURITY

In the previous section, a family of graphs has been considered which are associated with a family of matrices. We observe an interesting result by using tabulation along with the different parameters of the above graphs, which may be useful in information system's security, administrative structure, & defense and in communication and transportation problems. These graphs have also been used in construction of secret sharing schemes and compartmentalized and hierarchical secret sharing schemes. Table is giving as follows:

Table of the Above Graphs

S.No. Parameters	Graph - 1	Graph - 2	Graph - 3
1. Security	High	Low	High
2. Costing	High	Low	Medium
3. Reliability	High	Low	Medium
4. Manpower Requirement (Technical)	High	Low	Medium
5. Technical Support High	Medium High		

The above table shows that Figure 1 has the higher ranking in all the parameters and it is suggested that VLSI can use this network information's security system depend on the information. Figure 2 shows the lower in the parameters and it can use in SSI depend on the budget. Figure 3 shows the medium but high in security and technical support and it is suggested that MSI can use this security system.

No single control guarantees security by itself. Every security control is imperfect. Even if a security control is configured perfectly, which is generally impossible, and its software is free of bugs, which is also impossible, no single control can protect information system against all possible types of attacks. Some controls are designed for prevention, others for detection and response. Although no single control can be trusted to provide total protection, each control has its own unique place within security architecture. This approach is called defense-in-depth or a layered system of defenses architecture. The basic principle behind this approach is that even if the hacker can crack the first line of defense, (s)he is likely to be stopped by the second or third layer. For example, if a hacker passes through the firewall to enter the system, other security layers, like a manual monitoring or intrusion detection system (IDS), will try to catch the hacker before the damage is incurred fully.

It showed that both complementary and substitution effects might exist between information system's security technologies. By considering a security architecture that includes both a firewall and IDS, they show that the firewall and the IDS may complement or substitute for one another depending on the information's security and the detection rate of the IDS.

CONCLUSION

Effective information's security is the foundation of a secure operating environment. We pointed out here that three important aspects of graphs for security measurements can be generated the security codes & certain authentication. Thus, classification concept of graphs on information's security system will well satisfy the co-ordination of remote information which extends to security and emerging technology and in present era, it may be suggested for future work on industrial and other relevant areas.

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